

Business strategies towards Climate-Smart Agriculture in Europe

Practice Abstract

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Region(s)/Countries:

20 countries, with highest concentrations of studies in **Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, France, and Spain.**

Actors/Stakeholders:

Farmers, agri-food businesses, policymakers, consumers

Audiovisual Material:

[Link](#)

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Business strategies play a vital role in the agri-food sector's transition toward climate-smart agriculture (CSA), defining how value is created, shared, and captured while aligning economic, social, and environmental goals. They guide farmers and other agri-food actors in adopting innovations that enhance productivity, adaptation, mitigation, and resilience. At the same time, they coordinate collaboration among diverse stakeholders, such as farmers, cooperatives, policymakers, and consumers, ensuring that responsibilities, risks, and benefits are fairly distributed.

By integrating sustainability into everyday operations and supporting both formal institutions and informal networks, business strategies enable knowledge exchange, resource pooling, and collective investment in CSA practices. Without well-structured business strategies, many farmers lack the capacity or incentives to adopt new technologies and approaches. Effective strategies therefore link innovation with practical implementation, accelerating the shift toward a more sustainable and resilient agri-food system.

Needs addressed by the practice

Effective business strategies that operationalise the principles of CSA in the European context. It responds to:

- ▶ the challenge of integrating profitability with environmental and social sustainability
- ▶ helping farmers and agri-food businesses overcome financial, informational, and institutional barriers to adoption.

Methodology used

This report combines findings from a literature review on business strategies related to climate-smart agriculture, covering 142 peer-reviewed publications from 2000–2022. A systematic content analysis identified key strategic patterns, stakeholder roles, and governance mechanisms that enable CSA adoption in Europe.